

The Effect Of Social Media On The Travel Decision-Making Process For Glamping Businesses

Glamping İşletmelerine Yönelik Seyahat Kararı Verme Sürecinde Sosyal Medyanın Etkisi

İrem Ünal

Anadolu University, Graduate Schools and Institutes, Department of Tourism Management
irem.unal9@gmail.com

Duygu Yetgin Akgün / Assoc. Prof. Dr.

Anadolu University, Faculty of Tourism
dyetgin@anadolu.edu.tr

Abstract

Glamping is a tourist product developed for those who want to have a camping holiday in nature with a few of the comforts and luxuries of home. This study aims to determine the effect of social media on the travel decision-making process for glamping businesses. In this context, semi-structured interviews were conducted with volunteer individuals who have stayed at glamping establishments at least once through social media. In the analysis of the data, a qualitative data analysis program was used to perform a content analysis. As a result of the analyses, three themes were obtained; Pre-Trip, During-Trip, and Post-Trip. Pre-Trip, it was determined that individuals mostly examined the visuals related to the physical structure of glamping rooms on social media and comments regarding hygiene and the interests of the employees. All participants in the study stated that they used Instagram the most to find out information about the glamping business they wanted to visit. During-Trip, it was concluded that there was no difference between the service received by the individuals and the actual service. Post-Trip, it was determined that individuals shared their experiences on their social media accounts and these posts were mostly related to the architectural structure of their rooms. Participants stated that they would like to go back to glamping businesses as soon as possible Post-trip and recommend them to other individuals to influence them to go. As a result of the research, it was determined that individuals benefitted from social media at every stage of their trips.

Keywords: Travel Decision-Making Process, Glamping Businesses, Social Media.

JEL Codes: Z33

Özet

Glamping, doğanın içerisinde konfor ve lüksten ödün vermeden tatil yapmak isteyenlere yönelik geliştirilen turistik üründür. Bu çalışmanın amacı glamping işletmelerine yönelik seyahat kararı verme sürecinde sosyal medyanın etkisini tespit etmektir. Bu kapsamda sosyal medya aracılığıyla glamping işletmelerinde en az bir kez konaklayan gönüllü bireyler ile yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmeler gerçekleştirilmiştir. Verilerin analizinde bir nitel veri analiz programında içerik analizi yapılmıştır. Yapılan analizler sonucunda, Seyahat Öncesi, Seyahat Sırası ve Seyahat Sonrası olmak üzere üç tema elde edilmiştir. Seyahat öncesinde bireylerin, sosyal medyada glamping odalarının fiziksel yapısı ile ilgili görseller ile hijyen ve çalışanların ilgisi ile ilgili yorumlara daha çok incelediği tespit edilmiştir. Araştırmaya katılan tüm katılımcılar, ziyaret etmek istedikleri glamping işletmesi hakkında bilgi edinmek için en çok Instagram'ı kullandıklarını belirtmişlerdir. Seyahat sırasında bireylerin aldıkları hizmet ile gerçekleşen hizmet arasında bir farklılık olmadığı sonucuna varılmıştır. Seyahat sonrasında ise bireylerin yaşadıkları deneyimleri sosyal medya hesaplarında paylaşım yaptıkları ve bu paylaşımların çoğunlukla odanın mimari yapısı ile ilgili olduğu belirlenmiştir. Katılımcılar gezi sonrasında glamping işletmelerine en kısa zamanda tekrar gitmek ve diğer bireylere de tavsiye ederek gitmeleri konusunda etkilemek istediklerini belirtmişlerdir. Araştırmanın sonucunda bireylerin seyahatlerinin her aşamasında sosyal medyadan yararlandıkları tespit edilmiştir.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Seyahat Kararı Verme Süreci, Glamping İşletmeleri, Sosyal Medya

JEL Kodları: Z33

1. Introduction

Countries can benefit from the potential effects of tourism by diversifying tourism. Today, tourists have turned towards different expectations instead of mass tourism and this has led to alternative tourism (Çelik et al., 2020). The demands and needs of tourists have changed over time and therefore, products and services have been differentiated. In this context, businesses have introduced products and services suitable for the expectations and wishes of tourists (Albayrak, 2013). Recently, tourists prefer to get away from crowds, prefer natural areas and outdoor recreation (Craig, 2020) and tend towards glamping. Glamping is an alternative holiday concept for individuals who find it troublesome to go camping, as it does not contain the laborious work and experiences of normal camps (Hrgović et al., 2018). In addition, glamping, which is preferred for relaxing and spending time with animals, is a tourist product that is realised in nature without sacrificing luxury and comfort (Brochado & Pereira, 2017).

Sustainable tourism practices have gained importance in recent years for the continuity of the tourism industry (Düz, 2022; Sevinç & Duran, 2018). Among the criteria that show that an enterprise attaches importance to sustainability are supporting it with technological applications, involving stakeholder groups and local people, and the use of local resources (Kavak & Emir, 2022). Glamping businesses are environmentally friendly businesses that are conscious of sustainability as well as luxury and comfort. The concept of glamping and sustainability includes several features: the eco-friendly design and maintenance of the facility; sustainable management; specially grown hormone-free products; the use of compost toilets; the transformation of waste; the use of renewable energy; accessibility; the use of regional products and services; and the cooperation of local people (Walter & Comino, 2014; Korkmaz, 2019; Schneegans, 2022). The services provided by these businesses and the activities they offer are in line with an understanding of sustainability. In addition, tourists staying at glamping businesses are intertwined with local people compared to other operating accommodation businesses. This situation increases the welfare of the local people, as well as the development of the infrastructure of the region and the opening of new businesses. Therefore, glamping businesses provide social and economic development by ensuring their sustainability (Demir & Demircioğlu, 2023).

Nowadays, one of the ways to reach a glamping business is through social media interaction. Travelers can also instantly share their experiences on social media Pre-Trip, During-Trip, and Post-Trip (Munar & Jacobsen, 2014). Individuals conduct various searches to gain prior information with regard to the accommodation establishments they will visit (Filiari

& McLeay, 2013). Actively used information technologies allow the obtaining of information regarding the business, looking at alternatives and learning about the experiences of other users. In recent years, social media has been effective in shaping consumers' destination perceptions and trip decisions (Di Pietro et al., 2012; Kasapoğlu et al., 2023). The decision-making process is no longer specific to the pre-travel phase, but it is known that consumers make dynamic decisions with the help of social media platforms (Varkaris & Neuhofer, 2017).

On the other hand, institutions and organisations can direct users with the pictures, videos and content they share on social media (Oyman, 2016) and create positive perceptions regarding products and services, meet needs and increase brand awareness (Mason et al., 2021). In this respect, posts containing tourist experiences on social media platforms trigger the user to have positive information about products and services or to show purchasing behaviour (Eryılmaz & Şengül, 2016; Lund et al., 2018). The idea of how effective social media channels are in tourists' preference for glamping businesses is the starting point of this study. Travelers share both positive and negative information on social media, but it is important to note that a company's timely and helpful response to a negative post can mitigate its negative impacts and increase the trust of potential customers in the location (Schmallegger & Carson, 2008). Businesses that realize the advantages of social media channels increase brand awareness and direct consumers to purchase using social media effectively (Mason et al., 2021). In light of this situation, This study aims to determine the effect of social media on the travel decision-making process for glamping establishments.

Due to the intangible nature of the tourism sector, where competition is constantly increasing day by day, tourists engage in intensive information-seeking activities in order not to be mistaken in their travels, to be sure of the perceived service and to make more rational decisions. This information-seeking, together with different information-seeking strategies, reduces risks by responding to perceived uncertainty. Glamping, a popular and new tourism trend of recent times, is a type of holiday that combines being in touch with nature with luxury and comfort. Since luxury tents, nature views and unusual decorations offer visually striking content, guests tend to share these moments on their social media accounts. Tourists, who avoid taking risks during their holidays, actively use social media at every stage of their glamping experience, both to obtain reliable information and to seek social approval and validation by sharing their experiences. When the studies on glamping were examined, it was determined that there are studies on similar and different aspects of glamping regulations enacted in Türkiye and Greece (Ceylan et al., 2023), sustainable food

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understanding in glamping businesses (Güvenol & Kömürcü Sarıbaşı, 2022), glamping tourism after the COVID-19 pandemic (Craig & Karabas, 2021; Cebeçi, 2021; Düzgün, 2021), expectations and satisfaction with glamping (Yetgin Akgün & Ünal, 2021), and the glamping experience (Brochado & Brochado, 2019). When the literature was examined, no study was found that investigated the effect of social media on tourists' preference for glamping businesses. In this context, this study is important in terms of its scientific contribution to the literature and the related sector. This study aims to fill the gap in the existing literature. It is expected that this research will lead to further research on glamping. It is recommended that entrepreneurs should understand the behavior of tourists on social media to make important strategic decisions when creating social media marketing strategies.

2. The Conceptual Framework

Conceptual and Theoretical Background

The speed of change in the world order leads to innovation in the information sector as in every field. Information technologies, which are constantly developing due to their structure, have brought many changes in the way both social life and business life handle things (Bulunmaz, 2011). Although many new concepts have entered our lives with these changes, the most talked about in recent years is social media. As the usage areas of social media continue to change and expand, the definition of social media is also changing (Zeng & Gerritsen, 2014).

Social Media Platforms

Social media is a group of internet-based applications based on Web 2.0, where users can easily create a profile and post, and this post allows the exchange of information between other users (Boyd & Ellison, 2007; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Social media are dynamic, integrated, egalitarian and interactive organisms that are not under the control of any organisation (Peters et al., 2013). Social media, one of the most preferred online environments, has been incorporated into the social and economic order around the world (Zeng & Gerritsen, 2014). Rich content prepared by businesses influences existing and potential customers. Thanks to this effect, individuals will form positive attitudes toward a business in the future (Hanna et al., 2011). It plays a major role in the future of a company by increasing the reputation and sales of the company (Kietzmann et al., 2011). So that the number of active social media users is 4.7 billion, which is 59.4 percent of the world population (Kavak & Emir, 2023).

With developing technology, new social media platforms are coming onto the market and the features

and forms of existing social media platforms are changing. While a number of social media platforms have photo or video-sharing features (Boyd & Ellison, 2007), others include both photo and video-sharing. Although the characteristics of social media platforms are sometimes similar to each other, each platform has a style specific to the language and culture of its user base. In this respect, social media platforms vary in function and scope.

YouTube, a video-sharing website, was created in 2004; Twitter, a simplified microblog, was created in 2006; WhatsApp, a messaging and search application developed for smartphones, was created in 2009; Instagram, a photo-sharing network, was created in 2010; Tinder, a dating application, was created in 2012; and Tiktok, a music and video content, was created in 2016.

The Importance of Social Media for Tourism Businesses

The tourism world has turned towards digital transformation in the face of technological developments. It has started to use tools such as personalized experience, data-driven approach, multi-channel customer experience, and social media platforms in its operations (Yüksek & Kalyoncu, 2020). As in every industry, social media, which is used as a fast and low-cost way of reaching a target audience, is widely used in the tourism industry. Social media enables businesses to develop sales channels, increase brand and image awareness, carry out advertising and promotional activities, and strengthen customer relations (Çiftçi, 2016; İmre, 2020). Posts on social media platforms that include tourist experiences trigger the user to have information regarding products and services or to show purchasing behaviour (Eryılmaz & Şengül, 2016). The success of social media posts in global interaction and their reach to many segments affect individuals' destination choices (Sevinç, 2021). Through social media platforms, users take purchasing action if the comments they read about the tourism business they want to get information about are positive (Lund et al., 2018). Verma et al. (2012) found that travelers exhibit a decreased propensity to reserve hotel accommodations in the presence of unfavorable reviews, whereas Almana and Mirza (2013) illustrated the significance of highly rated reviews in shaping purchasing decisions. In this context, social media is a tool that tourism businesses should include in their marketing strategies (Coelho et al., 2016).

Tourism operators should be able to use social media before a trip (to inspire, inform, interact), during the trip (to provide convenience in the destination) and after the holiday (to remember, share and interact) (Popescu, 2014). In addition to their significant role in people's daily lives and social contexts, social media have become an indispensable aspect of tou-

ism. At these crucial stages of information-seeking and decision-making, social media is reshaping how consumers seek, discover, read, trust, and share information (Varkaris & Neuhofer, 2017).

The Glamping Concept

The consumption frenzy experienced in recent years has led the tourism sector to new searches in every sector. In addition, trends following individuals' desire to have a different holiday experience (Yetgin Akgün & Ünal, 2021), wanting a socially distanced holiday (Düzgün, 2021), and wanting to escape the crowd (Craig, 2020) have revealed glamping, the touristic product type that has gained momentum in recent times. Glamping is defined as 'accommodation that is more comfortable and expensive than that usually used for camping' (Brooker & Joppe, 2013).

Glamping, which is more modern than normal camping, offers an 'open-air hotel' experience where people can engage in activities by combining camping and luxury in nature within the scope of environmental respect and sustainability without the need to take the items that may be needed in camping, such as sleeping bags, tents and food (Birdir et al., 2015; Brochado & Pereira, 2017; Taino, 2018). Glamping aims to provide guests with high levels of comfort (Olcay & Turhan, 2017).

Glamping is a tourist product that combines luxury and nature, comfort and respect for the environment in outdoor tourism. The professional, hotel-managed businesses of this type of tourism are called glamping businesses. Glamping businesses have started to operate more and more around the world (Eremić, 2020). According to the report published by Grand View Research on the glamping market, it is estimated that the size of the global glamping market was 2.68 billion dollars in 2021, and will reach 7.11 billion dollars from 2022 to 2031. Despite this, glamping has not yet reached the desired level in Türkiye (Ergüven et al., 2015; Göktaş et al., 2017).

Features of Glamping

Glamping, which combines nature, comfort and many different accommodation styles under one concept in the context of experiencing new things and adding extra value, especially as the starting point of special interest tourism types, has spread to a wide geography that will fulfil the expectations of many segments (Kaya & Ergüven, 2022). Glamping businesses allow you to be in nature, away from the hustle and bustle of life, with its sea, landscape and forest. Businesses that provide glamping services have different features compared to camps that require effort, such as setting up tents, cooking, collecting wood and lighting fires (Yetgin Akgün & Ünal, 2021). According to Sakacova (2013), the characteris-

tics of glamping tourism consist of quality service, respect for the environment, nature, and luxury.

Nature, one of the features of glamping, promises to provide an unforgettable experience by integrating with natural areas that have not been explored before (Petruša & Vlahov, 2019). When it comes to the concept of glamping and sustainability, it includes the eco-friendly design and maintenance of the facility, hormone-free products, the use of compost toilets, the use of renewable energy, the separation of garbage for recycling, and the cooperation of local people (Korkmaz, 2019; Schneegans, 2022). The concept of luxury in glamping businesses includes accommodations that will attract consumers by combining comfortable places with extraordinary natural environments and providing a customized service specific to the tourist (Filipe et al., 2018). In addition, it includes high-quality services such as spa, massage, cleaning and laundry services, and transfers (Sakacova, 2013). Glamping has no distinctive features compared to camping and is only focused on luxury and comfort.

The Luxury Tent Facilities Qualifications Regulation of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism entered into force after being published in the Official Gazette dated 23 September, 2022. According to this regulation, glamping businesses will be sustainable and environmentally friendly accommodation units that prioritize luxury and comfort from the establishment stage, taking into account energy efficiency and safety measures. In this context, investing in glamping businesses in Türkiye, with a market size that is expected to increase gradually, will be beneficial for both entrepreneurs and the tourism sector.

Although the regulation is only for luxury tents, glamping architecture is more inclusive than that. Tourists are offered glamping architecture in different styles. These architectural structures consist of vernacular structures (caves and igloos), domes and bubbles, tents (bell tents, safari tents, luxury tents, red tents, and yurts), tree houses and cabins (wooden huts, a-frame cabins, eco-capsules, high cabins, huts, and tree houses) and originally designed structures (gypsy caravans, caravans, floating houses, hobbit houses, barns, wagon houses, castles, towers, and boats) (Korkmaz, 2019; Önem, 2019; Kılınç, 2021).

Glamping Tourist 'Glamper'

Tourists who prefer glamping establishments are called 'glampers'. 'Glampers', in other words glamping tourists, prefer to escape their daily lives, to stay alone, to relax, to be in a peaceful and calm environment, and to be intertwined with animals (Petruša & Vlahov, 2019; Yetgin Akgün & Ünal, 2021). Glamping tourists are young and high-income individuals with a high level of education (Milohnić et al., 2017), who adopt a healthy lifestyle (Ergüven et al.,

2015), like to explore new places, and want to be close to nature (Sommer, 2020). While these individuals want to receive high quality luxury services, they do not want to carry their belongings for accommodation (Ergüven et al., 2015). They are also individuals who wish to experience adventurous activities while wanting to experience extraordinary accommodation (Sommer, 2020). These activities can be diversified as fishing, canoeing, hiking, bird watching, yoghurt, stargazing, wine tasting, ATV tours, horse riding, paragliding, climbing, meditation, ceramic painting, water sports, massage, mountain climbing, and mountain biking (Yıldırım & Erkiş, 2019). The activities offered by glamping businesses can vary depending on the geography, country, and culture where the business is located.

3. Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative research method was preferred to examine in depth the opinions of people staying in glamping businesses through social media. Qualitative research is a form of approach that examines every subject that falls within the scope of social and cultural phenomena and individuals' experiences and thoughts (Toker, 2019). The common point of qualitative research is that it focuses on understanding and meaning-making (Merriam, 2009). A phenomenological design was preferred in this study. Phenomenology aims to create in-depth meaning with regard to lived experiences, in other words, to determine the essence of common experiences (Patton, 2018). Before starting this study, approval with protocol No. 232126 was obtained from the Anadolu University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee.

Participants

In the research, the criterion sampling technique was first used to determine the participants of the interviews. With this technique, which is preferred because it allows the researcher to select suitable individuals according to predetermined criteria (Merriam, 2009) to obtain the information he/she wants to obtain, individuals who have stayed at glamping establishments at least once through social media were included in the participant group. After reaching the first five participants, the snowball sampling technique was applied to select new participants (Patton, 2018). In this way, the participants were asked who else could be interviewed and information about the new participants was tried to be obtained. According to Creswell (2013), snowball sampling focuses on people and critical situations where rich data can be obtained and the universe can be reached by following these people and critical situati-

ons. A total of 25 participants were interviewed until data saturation and depth were reached, and then the data collection process was terminated (Patton, 2018).

In this study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with volunteer individuals who stayed at glamping businesses at least once through social media. The semi-structured interview technique was preferred in order to carry out the interviews with a certain degree of consistency and to address all aspects of the research topic. In order to conduct the semi-structured interviews, the seven-stage procedure suggested by Kvale (2007) was applied. These seven stages consisted of thematization, design, conducting the interview, transcription, analysis, verification, and reporting.

Data Collection Tool and Process - Interview Process

In order to determine the participants to be interviewed, the volunteers were asked, 'The name of the glamping business they have stayed in before' and 'Whether they used social media platforms when choosing this business'. After determining the participants to be interviewed according to these criteria, each of them was first contacted by phone, face-to-face or e-mail using their contact information. Before these interviews, the participants were informed about glamping and social media. A signed voluntary participation form was delivered to the researcher face-to-face or by way of e-mail before the interview.

The face-to-face and online (Zoom Platform) interviews were conducted with a total of twenty-five Turkish people between 20 April and 25 May 2022. The interviews varied between seventeen minutes and twenty-five minutes on average. The face-to-face interviews were audio recorded and the online interviews were video recorded with the permission of the participants. According to Maxwell (2018), interview recordings should be listened to and notes should be taken before transcription. In this study, the interview recordings were listened to, notes were taken and transcriptions were carried out separately. The individuals participating in the research were listed as P1, P2, P3... and the participants were given codes between P1 and P25.

Validity and Reliability of the Study

The unique structure of qualitative research has led to the emergence of new concepts instead of validity and reliability. The most frequently used of these are the principles under the roof of Lincoln and Guba's (1985) concept of trustworthiness. These principles remain persistent in the literature. In qualitative research, Creswell (2013) recommends applying at least two or more of these principles in order to test the

accuracy of the data. The researcher visited a few of the glamping businesses and spent time getting to know the application area personally. The data obtained from the research were analyzed by two researchers who are experts in their fields and a consensus was reached. For the draft interview questions, expert opinion was obtained from two academicians, one of whom had previously conducted studies on glamping and the other who was an expert in qualitative research methods. The interviews with volunteer participants were recorded with a voice recorder and all the details were discussed beforehand. These interviews were fully transcribed. In this study, the researcher conducted content analysis in a qualitative data analysis programme and determined codes and themes with this program in order to shorten the data analysis process and to facilitate the control of the data (Miles & Huberman, 2019). In this way, the credibility of the criterion was ensured. In the presentation of the research findings, direct quotations including the views of the participants were included and reminder notes were kept in the diary during the interviews, thereby ensuring the criterion of transferability. The researcher was involved in the data collection phase and took notes. At the same time, all the authors were involved at all stages of the data collection and the data analysis process, and supervision was carried out. Therefore, consistency was ensured. For the confirmability criterion, the data were read separately and coded by different coders without being influenced by their beliefs and prejudices. As a result, the researcher reduced the risk of bias.

Data Analysis

The content analysis method was used to analyze the research data. The most important feature of content analysis is that it is a technique based on numerical data that can summarize and compare

the content of communication through the objective and systematic application of classification rules (Kassarjian, 1977). The researcher created transcripts after the data collection process was completed. The transcribed interview texts were carefully read more than once by the researcher. In the analysis process, the researcher started with inductive analysis but continued with deductive analysis when it was decided that Dwityas and Briandana’s (2017) ‘Social Media in the Travel Decision-Making Process Model’ was suitable for the research. With this model, the themes of the research emerged. After the readings, a code scheme was drawn by the researcher and coding was conducted. Categories were formed by combining the codes that were similar to each other and the themes were formed by combining categories. The data obtained in the study were examined by two researchers who are experts in their fields and a consensus was reached. Since the participants’ statements contained more than one code, the frequency of the codes was higher than the number of interviews. In the thematic analysis, there are three themes, ten categories and three hundred and eighty-eight codes.

4. Findings

Participant Profiles

The data obtained from the interviews with the participants were analyzed by the content analysis method. The findings regarding the demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1. The interviews were conducted with a total of twenty-five people; sixteen women and nine men. It was determined that the ages of the participants ranged between twenty-two and forty-two years. The most common educational status was undergraduate, graduate and high school graduation, respectively. It was determined that the participants went on vacation at twice and at most ten times a year.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants

Participant	Age	Gender	Profession	Educational Status	The average number of trips per year
P1	33	Male	Insurer	Postgraduate	8
P2	27	Male	Social media expert	Postgraduate	2
P3	36	Male	Academician	Postgraduate	4
P4	34	Female	Journalist	Undergraduate	10
P5	29	Male	Academician	Postgraduate	1
P6	25	Female	Insurer	Undergraduate	3
P7	25	Female	Insurer	Undergraduate	2
P8	26	Male	Taxi driver	High School	2
P9	42	Male	Tourism	High School	2

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P10	31	Female	Dietitian	Undergraduate	2
P11	24	Male	Accountant	Undergraduate	6
P12	22	Male	Photographer	High School	5
P13	35	Female	Cabin crew	Undergraduate	6
P14	28	Female	Teacher	Undergraduate	1
P15	38	Female	Teacher	Undergraduate	1
P16	32	Female	Tour Guide	Undergraduate	2
P17	39	Female	Engineer	Postgraduate	2
P18	40	Female	Tourism	Undergraduate	3
P19	27	Female	Social media expert	Undergraduate	2
P20	29	Female	Security guard	High School	2
P21	42	Female	Academician	Postgraduate	3
P18	42	Female	Tourism	Undergraduate	3
P19	27	Female	Social media expert	Undergraduate	2
P20	29	Female	Security guard	High School	2
P21	42	Female	Academician	Postgraduate	3
P22	33	Female	Academician	Postgraduate	10
P23	31	Male	Entrepreneur	Undergraduate	10
P24	27	Female	Teacher	Undergraduate	3
P25	31	Female	Social media expert	Undergraduate	4
P25	31	Female	Social media expert	Undergraduate	4

The distribution of the participants according to occupational groups is as follows; academician, tourism, insurance, social media specialist, teacher, entrepreneur, engineer, security guard, photographer, dietitian, accountant, taxi driver, cabin officer and journalist. It was determined that the average daily time spent by the participants on social media was five and a half hours. The social media tools that the participants used the most were Instagram, Twit-

ter, YouTube, Facebook, LinkedIn and Tiktok. In this study, Dwityas and Briandana's (2017) 'Social Media in the Travel Decision-Making Process Model' was used to determine the themes of the research. Three themes, namely 'Pre-Trip, During Trip and Post Trip', and ten categories related to these themes, as well as the codes that make up the categories, are given in Table 2.

Table 2. The themes, categories and codes of the study

Themes	Categories	Codes	Number of frequencies
PRE-TRIP	Awareness of The Concept of Glamping Being In	Nature	12
		Luxury camping	11
		Comfortable environment	11
		Peaceful environment	8
		Interacting with animals	5

PRE-TRIP	Comments Considered on Social Media	Employee interest	12
		Hygiene	12
		Hotel and room architecture	9
		Customer satisfaction	8
		Location	6
		Quality of food	6
	Visuals Considered On Social Media	Physical structure of the rooms	20
		The hotel's proximity to the sea	10
		Luxury furniture	9
		View	7
	Glamping Reasons For Preferring	To spend time in nature	11
		Being influenced by content on social media	10
		Socially distanced vacation	9
		Getting away from the crowds of the city	8
		Price and performance ratio	5
	Social Media Platforms Researched On	Instagram	25
		Trip Advisor	10
Google comment		7	
Facebook		2	
Booking		2	
DURING-TRIP	Service Promised on Social Media	Meeting Expectations	19
		Misleading visuals	5
		Poor quality service delivery	4
		Disrespect for nature	2
	Transfer Of Experience Feeling	Peaceful and calm	14
		The feeling of being free	5
		Being with animals	2
		Clean and comfortable environment	2
POST-TRIP	Emotions Experienced After Vacation	Campfire	2
		Satisfaction	12
		Willingness to go again	9
		Influencing others to leave	6
	Post vacation experience	Recommend to people	5
		Sharing	19
	The Subject Of Shared Images	Non-sharing	5
		Architectural structure of the room	15
		View	11
		Animals	11
Total Frequencies			383

According to Table 2, the themes of the study are listed as Pre-Trip (235), Post-Trip (93) and During-Trip (55) according to the number of frequencies. There are five categories under the Pre-Trip theme, two categories under the During-Trip theme and three categories under the Post-Trip theme.

Findings Related to the 'Pre-Trip' Theme

At the Pre-Trip stage, tourists plan the process before traveling. This stage consists of realizing the need for a vacation, searching for information, and reviewing accommodation options. Tourists can learn from the experiences of other tourists through various social media platforms (Dwityas & Briandana, 2017). Tourists share their experiences regarding the tourist products and services they benefit from on social media platforms, allowing others to have an opinion and influencing their purchasing behavior (Eryilmaz & Şengül, 2016).

In the pre-trip theme, to make the process understandable, the participants were asked questions regarding (1) the information they obtained about glamping businesses; (2) the reasons for preferring glamping businesses; (3) the social media tools they used to prefer these businesses; and (4) the social media images and comments that influenced their decision-making.

The category of 'comments considered on social media' indicates what information the participants want to learn. In this category, one of the most important factors affecting tourists' decisions was identified as 'Hygiene'. Regarding the hygiene code, P21 stated that he had paid attention to the comments about the cleanliness of the rooms and the general environment saying, "I wanted to learn whether the rooms and the general environment were safe and hygienic. Visitor comments affected me a lot." Another code that was paid attention to in the comments was 'Interest of the employees'. In this regard, P6 said, "The comments I pay the most attention to are the service and interest of the employees. I wondered what their attitude towards our slightest request was. The comments about peaceful and smiling employees also influenced my choice." Other interesting codes under this category are hotel and room architecture, customer satisfaction, location and food quality. Sample statements related to these codes are given below:

"Since the quality and taste of the food is as important to me as the architecture of the rooms of the glamping establishment where I will stay, I looked at the social media comments." (P25)

"I especially read the comments about the location of the establishment." (P14)

The category of 'awareness of the concept of glamping' is intended to measure the level of knowledge of the participants with regard to the concept of

glamping. In this category, the fact that glamping businesses offered accommodation in nature was frequently included in the statements related to the code 'being in nature'. P4 reveals her awareness saying, "When I think of glamping businesses, I think of luxury tents where I can stay in nature." Another code obtained was 'luxury camping'. P2 expressed this awareness saying, "I only knew that glamping is a more luxurious version of camping and that it is intertwined with nature." In addition to these codes, codes such as 'comfortable environment', 'peaceful environment', and 'intertwined with animals' also stand out. Sample expressions related to these codes are as follows:

"While staying in nature, it saves the trouble of carrying equipment and we can easily meet our basic needs." (P5)

"It is impossible not to have a peaceful environment because it allows accommodation in nature." (P16)

"I know that there is a comfortable accommodation style with animals in a modern luxury campground." (P23)

The category of 'attention-grabbing visuals on social media' aims to determine which types of visuals attracted the attention of the participants. Participant comments differ from each other. In the images that the participants examined with regard to the glamping establishments where they would stay, various accommodation types such as glass lanterns, wooden houses and bungalows were evaluated under the code 'physical structure of the rooms'. Regarding this code, P9 emphasized that the architectural photographs of the room were decisive in choosing the establishment saying, "I was curious about the architecture of the room where I would stay. I was more impressed by the fact that the room was shaped like a transparent geodesic dome tent in the photographs." Other visuals regarding the establishment were evaluated under the codes of the hotel's proximity to the sea, luxury furniture and view. Sample expressions related to these codes are given below:

"One of the points I paid attention to in the photograph was whether the hotel was close to the sea due to its location." (P5)

"I was impressed by the white fan-shaped dome tents and the hammock in front of the room with a fireplace, stove and bathtub." (P18)

"Since I am a nature lover, the view was very important. I had looked at the view of the hotel on social media before I went." (P23)

The category of social media platforms researched is related to the channels through which information concerning the business is gathered. It is noteworthy that all the participants used Instagram to search for information. The prominent codes of this category are Instagram (25), TripAdvisor (10), Google Reviews

(7), Booking (2) and Facebook (2). Sample expressions for these codes are as follows:

"First, I got information from Instagram by looking at location information, people who went, what kind of environment it was and general comments." (P2)

"Before entering every business, I examine both the photos and comments on TripAdvisor. I try to look at the best reviews and the worst reviews." (P20)

"After searching the words Izmir Glamping on Google, I looked at the reviews of the businesses that came up." (P24)

"I did a general research about the hotel thanks to Booking." (P9)

"Apart from Instagram, I followed them on Facebook. I found new glamping businesses through social media and I will go to them this year." (P4)

The reasons for the preference category indicates the reasons for which the participants prefer the glamping establishment they want to go to. In this category, the participants' desire to be in nature and to be intertwined with nature was evaluated under the code 'spending time in nature'. P12 stated the reason for choosing a glamping business saying, "I preferred it because it is completely intertwined with nature." Another code is 'being influenced by the content on social media'. P1 supports this by saying, "I am influenced by the remarkable advertisements, photos, and videos about the glamping business."

Other codes obtained are; having a socially distanced vacation, getting away from the crowds of the city, and the price and performance ratio. Sample expressions for these codes are given below:

"There is a site called Small Hotel on the social media. I found the glamping business from that site." (P21)

"In my research, I paid attention to the fact that the bungalows were comfortable and the bungalows were far from each other, and that is why I chose the establishment I went to." (P20)

"The main reason for choosing this type of business was that I wanted to get away from everything." (P15)

"The price was attractive compared to the service and it was a different concept." (P16)

Findings Related to the 'During Trip' Theme

The during-trip stage is defined as the experience of the tourist. This stage includes experiences such as accommodation, transportation, food, beverages, products and services such as cultural centers, entertainment centers, and cultural activities during the holiday (Dwityas & Briandana, 2017). Under the theme of the during-trip, the categories of the service promised before the stay in the glamping business and the transfer of the experience were obtained.

The service promised on the social media category aims to measure the consistency between the service received and the service realized. The prominent code in this category was 'meeting expectations'. Regarding this code, the majority of the participants stated that there was no difference between the service they received from glamping businesses and the actual service. P16's statement, "There was no difference, it was exactly as we expected" supports this. In the statements evaluated under the code 'misleading visuals', it was determined that the glamping business looked different from the photos and videos on social media. P5 expressed this situation as, "The glamping establishment I went to looked much better on social media." The fact that the establishment was not clean, there was no contact person when problems arose, and the poor quality of the services provided in the establishment were evaluated under the code 'poor quality service provision'. Another code is 'Disrespect for nature'. Sample expressions related to these codes are given below:

"They are far from the service understanding I expected. The services were quite simple and of poor quality." (P17)

"I saw a group throwing cigarette butts on the ground at the hotel. They have no respect for nature." (P3)

The category of transfer of the lived experience is aimed at determining the experience of the participants during their stay in the glamping business. Under this category, the ability of tourists to rest during the holiday and the quiet and calm nature of the establishment were frequently included in the statements related to the code 'Feeling peaceful and calm'. P10 supported this code with the statements, "It was nice to be close to the sea, to sleep with the sound of waves and to wake up with the sound of waves, it was very peaceful." Another code is the 'feeling of being free'. P14 described this as, "I felt free to do anything." Other experiences were evaluated under the codes 'being with animals', 'clean and comfortable environment' and 'campfire'. Sample expressions related to these codes are as follows:

"One of the most enjoyable experiences I had was gathering around the campfire. It is a very friendly environment." (P13)

"It was an incredible feeling to spend time with the animals during my vacation, it was blissful, they were so well taken care of here and so used to people that they never ran away. They added color to my holiday experience." (P12)

"After the pandemic, I started to pay more attention to hygiene conditions. During my stay at the hotel, from the food to the general environment, everything was clean and comfortable." (P24)

Findings Related to the 'Post-Trip' Theme

The post-trip stage is the stage where touristic activities are completed. This stage includes tourists sharing their videos and photos about their experiences on social media platforms after their trips and their level of satisfaction with their trips (Dwityas & Briandana, 2017; Cheng et al., 2022).

The category of the subject of the shared images refers to the content of the images shared by the participants on their social media accounts after their trips. In this category, the code 'The architectural structure of the room' stood out. P8 mentioned the interestingly designed rooms of the glamping establishment saying, "I shared the transparent geodesic dome tent design of the room I stayed in on my social media." Other codes are 'Animals' and 'Landscape' photos. Sample expressions related to these codes are given below:

"I shared the cute little squirrel, the mascot of the glamping business, who did not leave my side during my vacation." (P6)

"I added unique nature views to my social media." (P1)

The category of emotions experienced after the vacation is related to measuring the satisfaction of the participants regarding the business and whether they intend to purchase the business again. The most repeated code in this category was 'satisfaction'. P17 expressed her satisfaction saying, "Staying at this glamping establishment was generally satisfying." P1's statement, "I am trying to arrange both the work environment and the friend environment so that I can go again" is an example of the code 'desire to go again'. Other important codes are 'influencing others to go' and 'recommending to people'. Sample statements related to these codes are given below:

"My circle of friends were influenced by me and went to the hotel where I stayed." (P13)

"It is an environment where they can experience luxury and camp life together. Therefore, I can recommend it to them." (P5)

The post-vacation experience-sharing category focuses on whether the participants shared their experiences in the glamping business. It was observed that the majority of the participants in the study shared their experiences on social media. In the statements related to the 'not sharing' code, the participants stated that they generally did not share on social media.

Discussion

The research findings would offer an overview of how glamping tourism consumers perceive, utilize, and process user-generated content on social media throughout the travel planning process. The par-

ticipants in the study stated that the definition they know most about the concept of glamping is luxury camping operating in nature. The recent popularity of the concept of glamping is because it operates in nature and has a luxurious and comfortable environment. The other definitions of glamping are comfortable environment, peaceful environment and intertwined with animals. In a study conducted by Güvenol & Kömürçü Sarıbaş (2022), tourists associated the concept of glamping with the words comfort, located in nature, accessible to basic needs, luxury, different from traditional camping, and calm, respectively. It is partially similar to this study.

According to the Digital 2022 Global Outlook Report, the daily time spent on social media in Türkiye is two hours and fifty-nine minutes. The most used social media platforms in Türkiye are Instagram, Facebook and Twitter, respectively. In this study, it was determined that the average time spent by the participants on social media was between one and ten hours and the most used social media platforms were Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, LinkedIn and Tiktok. Dogra & Karri (2020) found that tourists mostly use social media platforms of Tripadvisor and Facebook to get information regarding India.

It was concluded that the most effective reason for tourists to prefer glamping is that the businesses operate in nature. Filipe et al., (2018) found that the most important reason for choosing glamping was direct contact with nature. It was concluded that other important reasons for choosing glamping are related to social media content, wanting to have a socially distanced vacation, wanting to get away from the crowds of the city, and the price and performance ratio. This result is similar to other studies in the literature (Olçay & Turhan, 2017; Brochado & Pereira, 2017; Göktaş et al., 2017; Liberato et al., 2020; Craig & Karabaş, 2021; Düzgün, 2021; Meriç et al., 2021; Karadeniz & Özkan, 2022; Lu et al., 2022).

The participants in the study stated that they paid attention to the comments on social media while planning the glamping business they wanted to stay in at the pre-trip phase. The participants stated that they attached more importance to comments regarding hygiene and employee interest. According to Ulrich et al. (1991), the reason why the interest of the employees is taken into consideration so much is because the service provider has a big role in the tourist's experience. In a study by Gerenaz & Yetgin (2021), it was found that there were many detailed user comments concerning the cleanliness of the hotel. Other noteworthy comments included hotel and room architecture, customer satisfaction, location and food quality. In a study by Yetgin Akgün & Ünal (2021), it was determined that tourists have expectations regarding glamping accommodation architecture, friendly and caring employees, the beauty of nature and the scenery, and the taste of the

food. This is similar to this study.

Bizirgianni & Dionysopoulou (2013) concluded that young tourists are influenced by photos and videos shared for informational purposes on social media while making their trip decisions. It was determined that the visuals that the tourists in the study paid attention to on social media consisted of the physical structure of the rooms, the hotel's proximity to the sea, luxury furniture and the view, respectively. Giglio et al. (2020), in their study on luxury hotels, show similarities with the result that the visuals that tourists pay attention to most is the physical structure of the room. The participants stated that the difference between the service they received and the actual service was related to misleading visuals, poor quality service, and disrespect towards nature. This is similar to the study of Aşıroğlu & Çuhadar (2021). During their trips, the participants expressed their experiences as feeling peaceful and calm, feeling free, spending time with animals, being in a clean and comfortable environment, and chatting around the fire. A study by Yetgin Akgün & Ünal (2021) is similar to the sub-codes in the lived experience and luxury furniture categories.

Individuals share their experiences their post-trips on social media and therefore affect the opinions of their surroundings regarding traveling to a great extent (Aşıroğlu & Çuhadar, 2021). As a result, tourists can also lead to the emergence of a new travel trend by communicating their trips to large masses through social media (Doğan et al., 2018). In this study, the participants stated that they shared their post-trip experiences on social media. Likewise, Lu et al (2021) found that almost all of the people they interviewed within the scope of their study were willing to share photos of their glamping holidays on social media platforms. Another result of the research is that the images shared concerning glamping establishments are related to the architectural structure of the room, landscape and animals.

It was determined that the participants had high satisfaction levels with glamping establishments post-trip. It can be seen that this overlaps with similar research results in the literature (Aymankuy et al., 2012; Olcay & Turhan, 2017; Yetgin Akgün & Ünal, 2021). The other emotions experienced by the participants after their holidays are listed as the desire to go again, being effective for someone else to go and recommending it to people. The result of the guests' desire to go again is similar to the result of Brochado & Pereira's (2017) study on glamping experiences.

Conclusion

The idea of revealing the effect/determinant of social media on the travel decision-making process for glamping businesses constituted the starting point of this study. Businesses that realise the advanta-

ges of social media channels increase brand awareness and direct consumers to purchase using social media effectively. Marketing strategies in tourism should be flexible to adapt to ever-changing market conditions and customer expectations. Tourism marketing strategies such as innovative approaches, target audience analysis, digital marketing, providing personalized services, organizing events promoting local culture and effective use of technology are important in gaining competitive advantage. The combination of these strategies offers an effective way to both retain existing customers and reach new tourists.

In this qualitative research, semi-structured interviews were conducted with Turkish volunteer individuals who had stayed at glamping businesses at least once through social media. The data obtained at the end of the interviews were content analysed by a qualitative data analysis programme. In this study, Dwityas and Briandana's (2017) 'Social Media in the Travel Decision-Making Process' was used to determine the themes of the research. The themes identified are; (1) Pre-Trip, (2) During-Trip, and (3) Post-Trip. (refer to Fig. 1)

Pre-trip is an important theme in terms of the subject of this research. Individuals conduct research through various websites and online platforms to learn information about a product or service they want to buy (Cheung & Lee, 2012). All the participants in the study indicated that they used Instagram the most to find information regarding the glamping business they wanted to visit. Instagram, Tripadvisor, Google Reviews, Booking, and Facebook were ranked accordingly.

As much as the comments are written about a product or service before purchasing it, attention can also be paid to the images shared regarding that product or service. The participants emphasized that they paid particular attention to the physical structure of the glamping rooms. Luxury furniture in the room, the distance of the rooms to the sea, and the view were among the other interesting visuals. Individuals who want to engage in tourism activities act according to the information and thoughts they have acquired while choosing the hotel where they will stay (Cheung & Lee, 2012).

One of the most important results of this study is that the participants have detailed information about glamping. Participants defined glamping as businesses operating in nature, offering a more luxurious, comfortable, and peaceful environment than normal camps and allowing them to spend time with animals. The participants in this study stated that they prefer glamping establishments to spend time in nature. Other reasons for the preference of glamping businesses are the posts of individuals and businesses on social media platforms, the desire to go on a socially distanced holiday, to get away from the

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city, and the attractive amount paid according to the service received. In this context, glamping entrepreneurs need to analyze the target audience well. It should not be ignored that those who prefer this type of accommodation prefer to have a conscious

holiday in nature. In the study of Filipe et al (2018), the motivation source of glampers is direct contact with nature. Another source of motivation are the fact that the establishment is generally in a special and unique location.

Figure 1. The effect of social media on the travel decision-making process for glamping businesses.

Theoretical Implications

One of the most important results of this study is that tourists are influenced by social media when deciding to travel in a glamping business. Similarly, studies conducted in Türkiye, have determined that social media is effective on tourists' travel decisions and that tourists use social media platforms to obtain information about tourism destinations and tourism facilities (Doğaner & Armağan, 2018; Doğan et al. 2018; Güzel & Öztürk, 2018; Demiral & Gelibolu, 2019; Ünal & İpar, 2021). Xiang & Gretzel (2010) with American tourists, Bizirgianni & Dionysopoulou (2013) with Greek young tourists Li & Wu (2015) with Chinese tourists; Tao & Feng (2016) with British tourists; Baqain & Othman, (2018) with Malaysian tourists; Dogra & Karri (2020) with Indian tourists concluded that social media affects the decision-making process in tourism. It can be said that in this case, different cultures but the same results are observed.

According to Çiftçi (2016), social media also offers businesses, institutions, organizations, and other sectors the opportunity and convenience of promotion, sales, and marketing with a small budget. Thus, great opportunities are offered in terms of branding, image, and income. Innovation in tourism marketing through social media relies on new communication methods and technologies to achieve effective market positioning, enhance precision, and keep up with trends in the industry (Zheng, 2023).

Under the theme of the during trip, the service pro-

mised on social media and the transfer of the lived experience is included. When the data analyzed within the research scope were examined, most participants stated that the service they received from the glamping business coincided with the service they formed in their minds through social media. This is a remarkable result of the research. Although most participants stated that the service they received met their expectations, some disagreed. Misleading visuals, low service quality, and the fact that both the operators and the individuals staying in the accommodation do not p The experiences they had during their stay in the glamping business are unique for each individual. The participants stated that they were able to rest in peace and feel calm because the glamping establishments were quiet and calm. Other experiences the participants had during the trip were feeling free, spending time with animals, being in a hygienic, comfortable environment, and chatting around the fire.

Under the post-trip theme, whether the experience is shared or not, the subject of the shared images and the emotions experienced after the holiday are included. Individuals engaged in tourism activities use social media to share their post-holiday experiences (Erol & Hassan, 2014, p. 805). The participants in this study stated that they shared their post-holiday experiences on their social media accounts. These images shared by the participants are related to the architectural structure of the room. This is due to the luxurious and unique interior design of

glamping establishments. Other shared images are listed as the view of the hotel and the animals they spent time with during the holiday period. It was determined that the participants in the research were satisfied with the glamping business they stayed in. Other emotions experienced after the holiday are listed as wanting to go back as soon as possible, being effective for others to go and recommending it to people. Tourism fairs are important events that bring together alternative tourism stakeholders with both the sector and the buyer, just like every branch of tourism. Businesses that want to be recognized in the sector and the target audience take a step towards branding by taking part in such events.

Practical Implications

The findings and discussions of this study are useful to industry practitioners and academic researchers interested in using social media. Individuals get information through various sites and online platforms before deciding about their holidays. According to Leung et al (2013) given the important role of social media in both travelers' decision-making and tourism operations and management, a wealth of research on the application of social media in tourism and hospitality has been cataloged in peer-reviewed journals. As a result of this research, it was determined that people benefit from social media sites in obtaining information concerning the glamping business. By giving importance to social media marketing, businesses can both increase their sales revenue and save on marketing expenditures. Positive feedback and shares on social media encourage other potential customers to prefer the business. For this reason, glamping businesses should actively use their social media accounts, share regular and attractive content, and respond to customer comments quickly and effectively. It would be beneficial to create locations that encourage tourists to capture and disseminate images that showcase the appealing and aesthetically pleasing aspects of glamping businesses in harmony with nature. These locations should be photographed using natural light and high-resolution professional images and videos should be shared. The analytical tools provided by social media platforms enable the observation of content that receives greater interaction, the demographic characteristics of followers, and the hours of greatest activity. This data facilitates the formulation of a strategic plan. Additionally, advertisements can be targeted to specific groups, such as those who appreciate nature, camping, or luxury holidays, to reach potential customers.

With marketing strategies such as campaigns and discounts, businesses can increase brand awareness and reach a wider customer base. Glamping businesses can increase the number of followers by running a competition on social media and offering

a free stay to the follower who shares the best glamping photo. Offering special discounts or promotional codes only to social media followers can encourage them to book.

Events and competitions to be organized by glamping businesses on social media can also increase the interaction of users and strengthen their loyalty. Although it was determined that users mostly benefit from Instagram as a result of this study, it can be recommended to focus on different social media platforms suitable for marketing strategies. Glamping businesses can be recommended to work with professional social media experts to build a social identity suitable for their target audience. Since tourists are influenced by the posts regarding glamping architecture they see on social media, operators can focus on such visuals. It should emphasize what is unique about the glamping business.

Glamping businesses are businesses that should respect nature due to their structure (Yetgin Akgün & Ünal, 2021). To reach an environmentally conscious tourist, it is recommended that both individuals and businesses share posts that emphasize eco-friendly travel and low-carbon footprint holidays, indicating that they are sensitive to nature. One of the results of this study is that the images shared on social media can be misleading. Glamping businesses should reduce individuals' possible feelings of insecurity by preferring realistic images in their posts. Providing quick and courteous answers to questions from potential guests creates trust and increases the likelihood that customers will choose your business.

Social media posts and the comments of existing tourists who share their experiences significantly affect potential tourists' identification of alternatives and making purchasing decisions (Dwityas & Briandana, 2017). In particular, comments on social media platforms such as Instagram and TripAdvisor can help glamping businesses identify the deficiencies and aspects that need improvement in the fastest way possible. In this respect, glamping businesses should pay attention to the comments made about them on their social media accounts and interact with existing and potential tourists by responding to these comments quickly.

Glamping accommodations offer luxurious nature experiences, aesthetically appealing environments, and unique activities, creating an atmosphere that is very suitable for sharing on social media (Sun & Huang, 2022). Guests tend to share these moments on their social media accounts as luxury tents, nature views, and unusual decorations offer visually striking content. In addition, activities and adventurous experiences in nature make users want to immortalize their holiday memories and share them with others. Activities such as campfires and nature walks also increase the digital visibility of glamping by providing attractive content for social media. As a result,

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those staying in glamping businesses can use social media more interactively and visually orientated compared to traditional hotel types. This is associated with their tendency to both emphasize their personal experiences and to foreground values such as environmental awareness and sustainable tourism.

Limitations and future research

This study, which aims to determine the effect of social media in the travel decision-making process for glamping establishments, contributes to the literature. One of the limitations of the research is that interviews were conducted with individuals staying in glamping businesses through social media. In this context, the same study could be repeated by interviewing glamping operators in future studies. This future study could provide important insights for glamping professionals and entrepreneurs who want to understand the latest developments in the sector and the most effective strategies. Researchers can focus on this research topic in the future. Interviews can be conducted with tourists who have been informed about glamping businesses through the travel agency and have decided to stay there. It would help to understand the full landscape of travel decision-making if the study were extended to include non-social media users.

Another limitation of this study is that the data were collected in a short period of approximately two months. It may be recommended to conduct long-term studies in the future to observe the changes in the impact of social media on the travel decision-making process towards glamping businesses over time. Thus, deeper information about trends and changes in consumer behavior can be obtained. Another limitation of this study is that all volunteers participating were Turkish. Another suggestion is that the impact of social media on the travel decision-making process for glamping can be investigated in individuals from different cultures. Different results can be obtained by providing a broader perspective with comparative studies to be conducted in the future by considering cultural differences. Thus, a contribution can be made to the existing literature. A qualitative research method was used in this study. To provide a more comprehensive analysis of the effects of social media on travel decisions, the use of mixed-method approaches combining qualitative and quantitative data may be recommended for future research.

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